

“MARITES”: A COGNITIVE STRATEGY IN IMPROVING STUDENTS’ ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

Majority of the Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences students at Carrascal National High School have experienced difficulty in expressing their thoughts and opinions using an English language. Instead of improving oneself, he/she focused more on sharing hearsays and embodied the “marites” culture inside the classroom. As a result, the researcher took advantage on the idea of being “marites” and developed action research entitled, **“MARITES”: A Cognitive Strategy in Improving Students’ English Language Proficiency.**” The research is divided into two phases: the first two phases will be for the speakers and the remaining two phases will be for the listeners.

**For the speakers*

- a. **MA**ke research on the latest news.
- b. **R**ift the news by sharing it with your classmates.

**For the listeners*

- c. **TE**ll your comment.
- d. **S**hare your summary about the news.

The study utilized qualitative research applying phenomenological design and used content analysis to identify themes gathered from the interviews and observations conducted by the researcher. Triangulation techniques were also applied to measure reliability and validity of data. During the data analysis, majority of the participants

mentioned that the intervention has helped them improved their English language proficiency.

Keywords: *Marites, Qualitative Research, Phenomenological, English Proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

English is one of the most widely and commonly used language around the world. It opens a lot of opportunities to improve the quality of life. In fact, it is a lingua franca of international business operations that binds different nations to drive economic growth, and other international developments. As such, this language has a significant role in the academic and professional lives of individuals, making it an essential subject to be included in the educational curriculum of every country. People were taught on the various domains of language like the basic grammar rules, syntax, morphology, semantics, pragmatics, discourse, etc.

However, learning this language is not that easy specifically for those with different native language. Philippines for instance has Filipino as its official national language. Correspondingly, the country is home to between 120 and 187 languages including a wide range of native languages mainly from the Malayo- Polynesian language family group (Tirosh, 2021). This signified that using an English language for Filipinos could be challenging and puzzling considering that they are used to communicate with others in their day-to-day conversation by means of their own dialect. This dialect comes with sentences of unique syntax, morphology, etc.

Supporting the stated argument, Mancilla & Hisona (2019) stated in their study that most of the Filipinos have negative feelings when speaking or talking using the English language. Most of them have not enough confidence so that they feel anxious and embarrassed when they make grammatical mistakes.

Presently, looking at the situation of the Grade 11 HUMSS students in Carrascal National High School, English language proficiency is one of the challenges they encountered leading to poor academic performances especially during oral graded recitations. No doubt, students are rich in ideas and opinions, but they struggled in expressing their thoughts and point of views. In one of the studies of Leyaley (2023), she revealed that respondents' insufficient sentence organization and inaccurate pronunciation contributed to their passiveness in using an English language. More so, the respondents strongly agree that internal factors such as nervousness, lack of confidence and fear of making mistakes lead to their passiveness.

Considering the current problem, the researcher is determined to conduct action research that will allow the students to improve their English language proficiency by exposing them to the language. Though there is already an existing English subject in the curriculum, however, the researcher has been convinced that there is still a need to

reinforce the language to develop one's potential in using the English language. Hence, this research was done.

Furthermore, this intervention is a product of the researcher's daily observation of the behavior of the students inside the classroom. As a teacher, it was perceived that the students are good in telling stories especially on the latest happenings in and out of the classroom. They oftentimes embody the persona of being a "Marites" who consistently answered the question: "Mars, what is the latest?"

Since Filipinos have embraced the "marites" culture as a reflection of broader social and cultural trends in the Philippines, it has a potential advantage in the ability to disseminate and share information (Cuadra, 2023). As a result, the researcher decided to take advantage the Filipino culture to allow the students to share one latest news in front of the class using an English language. The classmates will then comment on something about the sentence construction, pronunciation, modulation of voice, clarity, etc. This intervention is a cognitive strategy that permits learners to link new information with the prior knowledge in facilitating the transfer of learning through the systematic design of information that includes summarizing meaning and organizing new knowledge (Priya, 2021).

Finally, this research has provided the learners the opportunity to speak in English while they are sharing something to their classmates and the others have summarized the news and made comments. This intervention became a part of their daily routine to expose them to the language, hence, develop their self-confidence in expressing their views and ideas in front of the class while improving their English language proficiency.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the intervention "MARITES" in improving the students' English language proficiency. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the common challenges encountered by the students in using an English language?
2. What are the impacts of having a poor English language proficiency to the academic performance of the students particularly in their oral recitation?
3. What are the effects of the intervention in improving students' English language proficiency?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher utilized a researcher-made "MARITES" Cognitive Strategy to improve learners' English language proficiency. This strategy is an intervention/treatment given to the subjects to determine its effectiveness. "MARITES" stands for:

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- c. **TE**ll your comment.
- d. **S**hare your summary about the news.

The intervention is divided into two parts: the first two phases will be for the speakers and the remaining two phases will be for the listeners.

The first part is to “**MA**ke a research” on the latest news in and out of the Philippines. The assigned student should choose a news that is credible and based on facts. The news should be based on the rubrics presented by the researcher and the link of the source must be sent to the researcher to check if it follows the standards. He/ She should take note on the primary details like the name of the prominent person, date, place, etc. to prevent misinformation. This phase will make the learner more responsible in searching for reliable information and not spreading fake news. A “*MARITES*” should be a *purveyor of truth and facts*.

The second part is to “**R**ift the news” by sharing it with the classmates. After writing the important details of the news, the student will stand in front of the class and retell the news by paraphrasing what happened. The student is allowed to glance at his/her notes for important information like the names, dates, etc. to prevent misinformation but the other information should be delivered based on the understanding of the student, hence, he/she is highly prohibited to memorize the news. This part encouraged the learners to comprehend what they have read and be confident in telling news to his/her classmates using the English language. The presence of the researcher/teacher during the activity is significant to make sure that there is no misinterpretation throughout the delivery of the news. This action research has gradually improved the self-confidence of the students as well as their delivery of thoughts and ideas. A “*MARITES*” should be *confident in sharing the news utilizing an English language*.

The third part is to “**TE**ll your comment.” This is for the listeners where they are encouraged to listen carefully to the news and take notes on the good points and bad points of the speaker such as the delivery, pronunciation, grammar, etc. This is the stage where constructive criticisms happen to help one another in improving the communication skills using an English language. A “*MARITES*” should *provide a clear judgment and evaluation*.

Lastly, “**S**hare your summary about the news.” One way to improve English language proficiency is to allow the listener to summarize the news if he/she understood the idea presented by the speaker. This part also practiced the listening and speaking skills of the students which are essential in the communication process. A “*MARITES*” is *excellent in summarizing the news to confirm if he/she got the correct information*.

The entire intervention will embody the typical “Marites” which majority of our students are fond of practicing regardless of time and place. Even if the teacher is busy discussing a lesson, few of them are still talking about something and/or someone. As a teacher, we cannot remove the “Marites” culture, but we can make it more advantageous and beneficial. With the easy steps of the “MARITES” Cognitive Strategy, we can incorporate this in our lesson plan as one of the activities that will encourage active participation among students to improve their English language proficiency while developing their self-confidence and self-esteem. Hence, the researcher is creating a good “Marites” who helps the students not just to enhance their English language proficiency but also serves as a role model in spreading factual information to prevent bullying due to misinformation and hearsays.

Furthermore, this intervention is anchored on the Theory of Social Interactionism based on the work of Jerome Bruner about social learning. This theory claimed that communicative interactions are necessary for language proficiency. It also believed that language is acquired as a result of interactions that help a person develop language (Vaidya, 2020). In case of this “MARITES” action research, English language proficiency is supposed to be developed by socialization where communication process takes place between the speakers and the receivers. Hence, the researcher believed that socialization using an English language as a medium of communication has a significant effect in attaining and mastering of the language.

The intervention has been carried out during the first and second quarter of second semester of school year 2023-2024 in Grade 11 HumSS students in Carrascal National High School.

A. Participants and/or Other Sources of Data and Information

This study was conducted in Carrascal National High School located at National Highway, Barangay Gamuton, Carascal, Surigao del Sur. Specifically, the study was piloted in the Senior High School Department employing 65 Grade 11 HumSS students of sections Makatao and Maka-Diyos.

This action research used both printed and online materials where credible and reliable news are available. The teacher who acted as a facilitator confirmed the legitimacy of the information as to prevent the spread of fake news.

The simulation of the intervention commenced on February 5, 2024 (Monday) as part of the Practical Research 1 class period to test the efficacy of the method. The “MARITES” Cognitive Strategy happened before the start of the lesson as a preparatory activity to generate interest in the discussion while encouraging the students to practice speaking in English as part of their training to improve English language proficiency.

B. Data Gathering Methods

In January 2024, the researcher conducted a pre-interview to the Grade 11 HumSS students about the common problems they encountered inside the classroom with regard to the English language proficiency. Their responses were listed and recorded. The result of the pre-interview became the foundation of the action research, and the researcher found out that majority of the learners have struggled in expressing their ideas using an English language which was ironic since HumSS students were expected to do well in using a target language.

On January 22, 2024, a copy of an action research proposal was presented to the Office of the Principal seeking his approval to conduct the research. On the same day, students were acquainted with the intervention covering the objectives and the procedures of the strategy. A letter to the parents was also given to ask permission. The teacher assigned students to look for legit news following the rubrics presented by the researcher and the link of the source was sent to the researcher to confirm that the news is factual. One news per day.

On February 5, 2024 (Monday) the implementation of the strategy started. During the intervention, 5 minutes of the class period was allotted for the activity. The assigned student served as the speaker and the classmates served as the listeners. The speaker provided a proper citation to the subject teacher/researcher to confirm the correctness of the information. All students have given opportunities to be a speaker and a listener however, a high priority was given to those who were really struggling in expressing their opinions/ideas using an English language.

In March 2024, the intervention continued following the same routine specified in the data gathering procedure. At the end of the month, one-on-one interviews were piloted to gather relevant data. This intervention ended in April 2024 a month before the end of the school year.

C. Data Analysis Utilized

Using a qualitative research design employing a phenomenology, a one-on-one interview between the students and the English teacher was conducted at the end of the month to determine the effectiveness of the strategy in improving students' English language proficiency. A set of interview questions focusing on the statement of the problem were asked and responses were written and recorded to minimize the tendency of selective data collection. For the qualitative analysis, the researcher analyzed the transcripts to develop themes subject for further examination through inductive analysis. After the initial themes emerged, responses were listed and read again to cite supporting quotations to strongly answer the research objectives.

To observe the validity and reliability of results, the researcher followed the triangulation technique where the proponent of the research also conducted an interview with the subject teachers to ask them if the students have shown improvement in their

oral recitation while utilizing an English language as their mode of communication. The “improvement” signified that even if the student has not yet mastered the grammar rules or pronunciation, but he/she has stood and tried to answer a question using an English language is already an improvement to be considered. Eventually, the student will get use to utilizing an English language during class activities.

Moreover, the researcher utilized informational saturation as the time when new points and findings are not been added to the available data. Thus, if the responses of the participants were identical to the previous responses, then longer interview was no longer required.

Finally, data collected from the participants were analyzed by the researcher with the help of the subject experts, coordinators and master teachers. The data was evaluated by applying a content analysis technique. Thus, the researcher underwent sorting of data and comparing different pieces of information to summarize the statements into useful information. This way, the researcher was able to determine if the “MARITES” Cognitive Strategy has improved the English language proficiency of the learners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three major themes emerged from the data gathered regarding the “MARITES” Cognitive Strategy in improving English language proficiency of the learners. These themes were: 1) common challenges, 2) impacts of having a poor English language proficiency, and 3) effects of the intervention in improving students’ English language proficiency. These themes are discussed as follows:

Theme One: Common Challenges

During the interview, some of the students mentioned that one of the challenges they encountered inside the classroom setting was their poor English language proficiency that made them incompetent especially during oral recitation. P1 said that “*Sir, kahadlok mag English kay basin ako kataw-an, bahala dili ako makagrado sa oral* (Sir, I am afraid to speak in English because maybe they will laugh at me, it is okay if I don’t get any point from oral recitation.) Another participant agreed to the statement of P1 when she said that “*dabo man gud sir diri kun mga perfectionists,*” (there are a lot of students here who were perfectionists). Based on the responses of the learners, truly a poor English language proficiency has been one of their common problems in the academe.

Moreover, P28 mentioned that “*Sir bisan jaoy ako idea magduha-duha ko muanswer kay way ako confidence kay di ako mahibayo mag English,*” (Sir, even if I have an idea but I am still doubtful to give my answer due to lack of confidence because I am not good in English.) P7 agreed to the statement by saying that, “*mga bright man gud ako classmates sir, masipog ko mutindog,*” (I have intelligent classmates and so I am hesitant to stand). One teacher has affirmed the statements of the learners when she said that “*Sir permi ra iton sila mag Bisaya mo answer kay magduha-duha kuno mag English,*” (Sir,

they responded using Bisayan language because they are reluctant to use the English language.) The responses of the learners provided the researcher an idea and the need to craft an intervention that allowed them to gradually build a confidence in using an English language and an intervention that promoted a tranquil environment where judgment and discrimination cannot grow and foster.

In the study of Khan, et al. (2020), they revealed that lack of confidence, lack of participation in the school program and lack of interest in the study were some of the consequences of poor performance of the students in English language at secondary level. This result was alarming since these are Humanities and Social Sciences students and they were expected to be good in expressing their opinions and ideas utilizing an English language.

The researcher understands that there are some students who are not really into speaking activities due to multiple intelligences but for HumSS students they should be exposed to English speaking environment where they are required to interact because one of the exits of senior high school curriculum is Employment and part of the hiring process is the conduct of interview where they need to speak up and possibly answer a question using an English language.

Lastly, P16 clearly stated that, *Sir, di ako usahay mo answer kay basin mali ako grammar*” (Sir, sometimes I chose not to answer because I thought I used grammar incorrectly.) It is prevalent inside the classroom that one of the reasons why students are hesitant to participate orally is that they were cautious with the grammar. According to Fareed (2016), students make mistakes in subject-verb agreement, pronouns, tenses, articles, prepositions and basic sentence structures. However, grammar ability can be improved through grammar-related activities such as this action research. With consistent exposure of the students in the language, they will soon improve their language proficiency. This claim of the researcher was approved by Teacher 2 who said that “*Basta ma expose lam ini sila sir sa jaon na subject sanan willing sila mahibayo, makat-on man gajod,*” (As long as the students will be exposed to the subject and they are willing to be educated, they will surely learn.)

Given the responses of the key informants, poor English language proficiency was the identified root of students’ less confidence, and low academic performance leading to a more problematic society in the future. Ending the enigma, MARITES Cognitive Strategy was implemented.

Theme Two: Impacts of Having a Poor English Language Proficiency

The study of Al- Zoubi (2018) recommended that students should be continually exposed to the English language through practicing English language daily to encourage them overcoming their weakness and improving their proficiency in acquiring English language. This recommendation was the basis of the researcher in conducting action research considering that the participants have mentioned some of the impacts of having a poor English language proficiency particularly to their academic performance.

P11 has responded that poor proficiency of the English language has a significant impact to their performances inside the classroom since some of the teachers have conducted graded oral recitations , “*Sir, dako an impact ng English language kay haod sa ako na dili mahibayo karajaw mag-English, usahay dili rakan ako mag answer na mazerong gajod,*” (Sir, there is a huge impact of English language because just like in my situation who is not good in English, sometimes I prompted not to answer the question and as a result, I have acquired zero points.) If this continues, students will fail the subject, and his/her future will be affected.

The sentiment of the participant was agreed by Teacher 1 who thought that “*Dapat gajod maka express sila in English kay English ako subject dili man pwd na mag-Bisaya permi,*” (They should express in English because English is our subject, and it is not advisable to keep on using Bisayan language.) Though the teachers have tried everything to help the students in learning the English language, but sadly, these students were already in the senior high school level, but they still found it difficult to utilize the English language in the communication process. As a result, these learners needed more additional reinforcements through the implementation of interventions.

In addition, P17 believed that “*dako gajod an advantage ng mga hibayo mag-English sir,*” (it is really advantageous if you know how to speak in English sir). According to the online page entitled “The Benefits of Learning English as a Second Language” in 2024, investing in developing strong communication skills especially in using an English language can result to better outcomes at school, work, or even in personal lives. It is indeed important that students regardless of their native language should learn and acquire English language that serves as an armor to face different walks of life. With language proficiency, one could be able to communicate with clarity and brevity giving him/her good grades in an oral graded recitation.

Lastly, P8 said that “*usahay sir gamay ako score sa mga quizzes kay waya ako makasabot sa question kay English man,*” (Sometimes sir, I have low scores in quizzes because I did not understand the question stated in English.) It is difficult for the students to get good grades if they cannot understand the questions during formative and summative assessments because of poor English language proficiency. Hence, it is important that learners should have a better grasp of the language for them to improve their academic performance.

Addressing the negative impacts of poor English language proficiency to the academic performances of the students, the researcher has developed an intervention entitled “MARITES: A Cognitive Strategy in Improving English Language Proficiency.

Theme Three: Effects of the Intervention in Improving Students’ English language Proficiency

Another essential theme arose from the study was the effects of the intervention in improving the students’ English language proficiency. It is believed that low achiever

students can transform into academically successful individuals if teachers prioritize the conduct of intervention programs in the classrooms (Subba, 2022).

However, the researcher did not expect a hundred percent improvement in the language proficiency of the learners considering that acquiring an English language cannot be learned within a short span of time. It is continuous learning and requires constant practice.

Nonetheless, seeing student trying his/her best to stand and express his/her ideas in an English language regardless of his/her grammar, pronunciation, etc. is considered an improvement.

In fact, according to P11, “*Sir tungod sa imo MARITES kay medyo maka-oral nako bahala man iton kun mali ang grammar,*” (Sir, because of your MARITES, I have somehow participated in our oral recitation even if I used the grammar incorrectly.) This statement has proven that because of the intervention, learners like P11 has realized the importance of English language proficiency in their academic performance. Another key informant said that “*Sir, because of your MARITES research, I have trained myself to express my opinions and ideas in an English language and I am happy that my classmates were given the opportunity to critique the way how I delivered my news and my pronunciation.*” The implementation of the action research has been productive and meaningful especially to the students who have started to develop self-confidence in utilizing English language in the communication process. Indeed, interventions play a crucial role in enhancing academic performance among students.

Furthermore, P23 mentioned that “*dili nako karajaw masipog sir, amora nagtinabangay na kami sa ako mga classmates para ma improve amo English,*” (I am no longer shy, it is like we are helping each other in improving our English language proficiency). With this feedback, the researcher is confident that the main purpose of the action research was realized and appreciated.

Moreover, P34 clearly said that “*with the help of MARITES strategy, I started to improve my academic performance by actively participating in oral recitations.*” Agreeing to the statement, T4 mentioned that “*Sir naningkamot na baya sila mo-oral bisan mahalata na jaon pay gajod need nila e improve,*” (Sir, the students are trying their best to participate in our oral recitation activities even if they are still a lot of things to improve.)

However, one participant P19 honestly said that “*Sir, way man effect sa ako an imo MARITES activity. Masipog ak ghaon,*” (Sir, your MARITES activity has no effect. I am still reluctant to use the language.) This response only proved that the intervention is not 100% effective considering that students have different learning styles, habits and multiple intelligence. An intervention may be effective to one but not to all. The result only signified that there is still a lot of room for improvement. Nevertheless, the researcher is optimistic that with the continuous implementation of the research can gradually improve students’ English language proficiency.

Conclusions

MARITES strategy aims to help students overcome inhibitions in English expression, nurturing their confidence and grammar proficiency. This approach creates opportunities for students to use English, encouraging frequent usage in alignment with Bruner's theory that interaction is crucial for language development. Through repetition exercises, students can distinguish subtle differences between spoken and written English, enhancing their oral skills and self-assurance during the interactive process.

As teachers, the researchers strive to provide our learners different platforms to help them improve their English Language Proficiency. "MARITES" Cognitive Strategy to improve learners' English language proficiency, is one of the many strategies of educators to aid our diverse learners. As language learning and the learning outcome are conceived to be complex, dynamic, nonlinear, and variable where learners would encounter difficulties and challenges and thus need to persevere and remain interested.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author sought approval from the Office of the Principal of Carrascal National High School to conduct the action research to the Grade11 Humanities and Social Sciences (HumSS) students. Respondents were well-informed on the purpose and objectives of the research, and they have the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time as they wanted to. Parents' consent was also provided to inform the parents on the conduct of the research and that their children were considered as the respondents.

Respondents' identities were always kept confidential to safeguard the well-being of the students. The author also declared that there is no conflict of interest while doing the action research.

The author also attested to the originality of the research and has cited properly all the references used. Finally, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and the results were utilized purely for research.

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